

t, -CHO), 9.87 (1H, bs, COOH) (Found : C, 62.7; H, 9.2. Calcd. for $C_9H_{16}O_3$: C, 62.8; H, 9.1 %).

1,9-Nonanediol (5) :

The above compound **3** (2.0 g) was refluxed with LAH (0.5 g) in dry Et_2O (50 ml) for 6 h, the mixture was cooled and 25 ml of water followed by 30 ml of 4 (N) HCl solution was added, and the organic layer was separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with diethyl ether (2 × 100 ml), and the combined ethereal solution were washed with water, saturated $NaHCO_3$ solution and brine, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to afford diol **5** (1.5 g) as a thick liquid, which was purified by column chromatography and purity tested by TLC. The compound gave negative tollens and -COOH tests; ν_{max} 2920.65, 2855.44 ($-CH_2$), 3450.83 cm^{-1} (-OH), absence of -CHO and -COOH absorptions in IR spectrum; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : 1.29–3.50 (14H, m, $(CH_2)_7$), 4.38 (2H, br, CH_2OH) (Found : C, 67.4; H, 12.4. $C_9H_{20}O_2$ requires : C, 67.5; H, 12.5%).

1,9-Nonanedioldiacetate (7) :

Compound **5** (1.09 g) was stirred with dry pyridine (10 ml) and Ac_2O (10 ml) at ambient temperature and left overnight. The reaction mixture was poured into ice cold water and then extracted with diethyl ether. The organic layer was washed several times with 10% dil. HCl followed by water, dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent gave **7** (0.89 g) as a liquid, which was purified by distillation at 210–215 °C (bath temperature)/0.27 mm; ν_{max} 2932.59, 2856.60 ($-CH_2$), 1738.93 cm^{-1} (-OAc); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : 4.0 (2H, br, CH_2OAc), 1.26 (4H, br, CH_2) (Found : C, 63.9; H, 9.7. $C_{13}H_{24}O_4$ requires : C, 63.9; H, 9.8%); MS (m/z) : 244 (M^+).

7-Hydroxyheptanal (2) :

Following the method reported by Reuter and Salomon², *threo* aleuritic acid (12.0 g) yielded **2** (4.7 g) as a liquid, which was purified through a column of neutral alumina eluting with diethyl ether; ν_{max} 2933.88, 2858.97 ($-CH_2$), 3421.97 (-OH), 1724.81 cm^{-1} (-CHO); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : 1.1–1.91 (8H, m, CH_2), 2.36 (2H, t, CH_2), 2.45 (2H, m, CH_2-CHO), 2.38 (1H, br, CH_2OH , D_2O exchangeable), 3.7 (2H, t, CH_2OH), 9.92 (1H, t, CH_2CHO) (Found : C, 64.5; H, 10.7. Calcd. for $C_7H_{14}O_2$: C, 64.6; H, 10.7%).

1,7-Heptanediol (4) :

2 (2.5 g) was refluxed with LAH (1.0 g) in dry diethyl ether (50 ml) for 6 h, the mixture was cooled and 20 ml of water followed by 30 ml of 4 (N) HCl solution. The aqueous layer was extracted with diethyl ether (2 × 150 ml) and the combined ethereal solutions were washed

with water, brine, dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent afforded 1,7-heptanediol (2.2 g) as a liquid, which was purified by column chromatography; ν_{max} 2930.85, 2856.95 ($-CH_2$), 3415.25 cm^{-1} (-OH), no (-CHO) absorption at 1724.80; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : 1.29–3.50 (10H, m, $(-CH_2)_5$), 4.38 (2H, br, CH_2OH) (Found : C, 63.6; H; 12.0. $C_7H_{16}O_2$ requires : C, 63.6; H; 12.1%).

1,7-Heptanedioldiacetate (6) :

Compound **4** (2.0 g) was stirred with dry pyridine (20 ml) and Ac_2O (20 ml) at ambient temperature and left overnight. Usual work-up with diethyl ether as earlier afforded **6** (1.7 g) as a thick liquid. The compound was purified by column chromatography; ν_{max} 2924.48, 2854.08 ($-CH_2$), 1743.29 cm^{-1} (-OAc); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : 3.96 (2H, br, CH_2OAc), 1.24 (4H, br, CH_2) (Found : C, 61.0; H, 9.2. $C_{11}H_{20}O_4$ requires : C, 61.1; H, 9.2%); MS (m/z) : 216 (M^+).

Mosquito repellent activity³ :

The compounds (**7** and **6**) were evaluated for mosquito repellent activity against *Aedes aegypti*, the vector of dengue and *Anopheles stephensi*, the vector of malaria. Laboratory bioassays, following modified protocol used by Frances *et al.*³, were carried out in barraud cages measuring 60 × 60 × 60 cm containing about 500 female mosquito (4–5 days old and starved for 8 h) drawn from cyclically maintained regular insectary at 27 ± 1 °C temperature and 70 ± 5 % relative humidity.

1,9-Nonanedioldiacetate at 1 mg/cm² dosage effectively repel *An. stephensi* mosquitoes upto 570 min and *Ae. aegypti* up to 90 min. Whereas, 1,7-heptanedioldiacetate at the same dosage recorded protection time of around 450 min against *An. stephensi* and around 420 min against *Ae. aegypti*. Both the compounds was more than twice as effective as citronella oil (a plant based repellent) used as the standard for comparison.

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